

SAFETY LEADERSHIP AND SELF-EFFICACY: ENHANCING SAFETY CULTURE IN THE MALAYSIAN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

Hamizi Hamdan ^{1*}, Rosli Mahmood ¹, Raemah Abdullah Hashim ², Nur Shazwani Rosli ³

¹ Putra Business School, Universiti Putra Malaysia, Jalan Universiti 1, 43400 Serdang, Selangor Darul Ehsan, Malaysia

² Unitar International University Malaysia, Tierra Crest, Jalan SS6/3, Kelana Jaya, 47301 Petaling Jaya, Selangor Darul Ehsan, Malaysia

³ Sunway University Malaysia, 5, Jalan Universiti, Bandar Sunway, 47500 Petaling Jaya, Selangor Darul Ehsan, Malaysia

*Corresponding author E-mail: hamizih@gmail.com

Received Date: 23/03/2024

Accepted Date: 20/05/2024

Published Date: 30/06/2024

ABSTRACT

The Malaysian construction industry is renowned for its substantial dependence on a considerable workforce, constituting approximately 12.4% of the nation's total workforce in 2021, the third highest among industries in the country. However, it has raised concerns, ranking fifth and sixth for accidents between 2019 and 2023 and exhibiting the highest number of fatal workplace injuries among industries. This study aimed to investigate the effect of self-efficacy on the relationship between safety leadership and safety culture within the Malaysian construction industry. To conduct the research, data were collected from 385 supervisors, engineers, and project managers employed by Grade G7 contractors registered with the Malaysian Construction Industry Development Board (CIDB) in four states in the Peninsular of Malaysia. A systematic random sampling method was employed, and data analysis was carried out using SmartPLS 4. The results revealed that safety leadership has a significant effect on safety culture, and self-efficacy played a significant mediating role within these relationships.

Keywords: self-efficacy, safety culture, safety leadership, construction industry

INTRODUCTION

The construction industry is also known as a labor-intensive industry since so many parties are involved in a construction project (Boadu et al., 2020). In 2021, the construction industry employed 12.4% (1,190,000 persons) of Malaysia's total workforce, the third highest after services and manufacturing industries (Arina Sofiah, 2023). The fact that the construction industry has one of the highest rates of workplace accidents is somewhat unsettling.

According to statistics provided by the Department of Occupational Safety and Health (DOSH) Malaysia, the number of construction accidents in Malaysia has remained relatively high over the past five years and there has been no significant reduction in the total number

of accidents in the construction industry (See Table 1). Between the years 2019 and 2023, accidents in the construction industry continued to rank between fifth to sixth highest overall. (DOSH Malaysia, n.d.).

Table 1. Occupational Accidents Statistics by Industry

Industry	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Manufacturing	4,948	4,506	4,269	4,514	4,181
Agriculture, Forestry and Fishery	1,176	979	973	895	1,064
Finance, Insurance, Real Estate and Business Services	406	327	285	373	584
Transport, Storage and Communication	389	311	292	248	342
Construction	326	206	217	148	159
Utilities (Electricity, Gas, Water and Sanitary Service)	258	220	207	189	151
Hotel and Restaurant	235	140	126	119	176
Wholesale and Retail Trade	87	128	187	119	147
Public Services and Statutory Authorities	99	77	74	77	119
Mining and Quarrying	60	39	56	37	28

Source: Adapted from the Official Website of Department of Occupational Safety and Health. <https://www.dosh.gov.my/index.php/statistic-v/occupational-accident-statistics>

Furthermore, Table 2 shows that the total number of fatalities in the construction industry reached an all-time high in 2019, after which it began a slight decline (DOSH Malaysia, n.d.).

Table 2. Fatal Occupational Injuries for All Industry in Malaysia

Industry	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Construction	84	66	65	59	45
Manufacturing	73	73	48	58	45
Agriculture, Forestry and Fishery	43	43	16	16	19
Transport, Storage and Communication	21	11	6	10	9
Finance, Insurance, Real Estate and Business Services	16	8	17	24	15
Utilities (Electricity, Gas, Water and Sanitary Service)	9	3	8	9	4
Mining and Quarrying	5	3	8	8	4
Wholesale and Retail Trade	0	1	2	2	0
Public Services and Statutory Authorities	3	3	4	0	0
Hotel and Restaurant	5	2	0	0	0

Source: Adopted from the Official Website of Department of Occupational Safety and Health. <https://www.dosh.gov.my/index.php/statistic-v/occupational-accident-statistics>

From 2019 to 2023, the fatality rate as a percentage of all accidents remained high, standing at 25.77% in 2019, 32.04% in 2020, 29.95% in 2021, 39.86% in 2022 and 28.30% in 2023. Safety experts and those with an interest in the industry are concerned about the high fatality rate in Malaysia's construction industry, which shows that the industry's safety and health situation is still very poor and falls short of expectations (Ishak & Azizan, 2018).

Workplace injuries and accidents can have a significant economic impact on construction companies, including increased insurance costs, lost productivity, and legal liabilities (Pillay & Haupt, 2008).

Research conducted by Fang and Wu (2013) and Mohammadi et al. (2018) demonstrated a notable improvement in safety performance attributed to a robust safety culture. Conversely, Odu et al. (2018) pointed out that the rise in work-related accidents can be directly linked to the absence of a strong safety culture within the workplace. Mohammad et al. (2019) found in their investigation of the Malaysian construction sector that lacklustre safety culture has hindered any progress in enhancing the industry's overall safety standards.

Safety leadership is recognized as an antecedent to safety culture (Indrayana et al., 2022). Qabool et al. (2021) discovered that ethical leaders, through self-efficacy, influence obedience to safety protocols.

This study offers valuable insights into the distinct cultural and organizational elements that could have shaped the relationship between safety leadership and safety culture in the construction industry of Malaysia. These findings could be extrapolated to other comparable settings. This study's analysis of the connection between safety leadership and safety culture gave industry professionals and policymakers important knowledge for developing and putting into practice efficient safety management plans. By identifying the particular characteristics that contributed to a positive safety culture, the Malaysian construction industry could have implemented focused interventions to improve safety outcomes and lower the number of accidents and injuries.

Through an analysis of the mediating role played by self-efficacy in the relationship between safety leadership and safety culture, this study contributed to the understanding of how people's perceptions of their abilities to perform OHS activities may have influenced their overall commitment to safety and safety culture. It might have provided direction for creating training curricula meant to boost individual confidence in their ability to carry out safety-related duties effectively. If workers felt more confident in their abilities, they might have been more committed to adhering to safety procedures and helped create a positive safety culture.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

SAFETY CULTURE

Choudhry et al. (2007) indicate that there is a plethora of academic definitions regarding safety culture, with many sharing considerable similarity in their fundamental beliefs. Each of these definitions places varying degrees of emphasis on how individuals perceive and/or behave towards safety. According to Wu et al. (2010), safety culture is defined as the employees' perceptions of safety conditions that impact safety outcomes. Perry (2016) describes safety culture as the culmination of individual and collective values, skills, perceptions, attitudes, and behavioral tendencies that shape an organization's dedication, as well as the approach and effectiveness of safety and health management. Establishing a strong safety culture in the workplace is essential to reducing the likelihood of accidents and hazards at work (Odu et al., 2018). However, the subdomain of organizational safety culture has gotten relatively less attention recently, with healthcare and patient safety culture emerging as the key area of study in the safety culture domain (Van Nunen et al., 2018).

SAFETY LEADERSHIP AND SAFETY CULTURE

One of the most important factors affecting construction site safety is leadership (Ma et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2016, 2017). It is believed that safety leadership has a critical role in encouraging workers to adopt safe behaviors, reducing accidents, and improving overall safety performance (Novaryan & Erwandi, 2024). Workers generally believe that there is a lesser likelihood of accidents when they work for organizations with strong safety leadership and culture as opposed to those with poorer safety leadership and culture (Novaryan & Erwandi, 2024; Oah et al., 2018).

A positive relationship between safety leadership and safety culture has been shown by multiple recent studies carried out in Indonesia in a variety of industries, including mining (Atikasari et al., 2022), construction (Machfudiyanto et al., 2019), and manufacturing (Khasanah et al., 2019).

The majority of the research indicates a favorable correlation between safety leadership and safety culture; nevertheless, others have reported inconsistent results or no discernible correlation at all. Saleh et al. (2015) showed that although teamwork scored highest on safety culture subscales, there was no correlation between it and safety outcome factors in their inquiry into nurses' perceptions of hospital safety culture and its effects. A similar pattern was observed in a study conducted by Lee and Quinn (2020), which assessed specific facets of the safety culture prevalent in East Asian hospitals and found shortcomings in staffing and the lack of a punitive response to failures.

Based on these results, the following hypothesis is put forth:

H₁: There is a significant effect between safety leadership and safety culture

SELF-EFFICACY AS MEDIATOR

Bandura (1997) defined self-efficacy as a set of beliefs held by individuals about themselves that determine their ability to execute a plan of action in hypothetical scenarios successfully. Self-efficacy, as outlined by Eden and Zuk (1995), refers to confidence in one's capability to accomplish a task successfully, irrespective of the circumstances surrounding its execution. According to Gardner and Pierce (1998), an individual's self-efficacy evolves over time through the accumulation of experiences.

Many studies utilize self-efficacy as a mediator to understand the impact of different leadership styles on various variables. Surprisingly, none have thoroughly examined the mediating role of self-efficacy on the relationship between safety leadership and safety culture. The closest study with similar findings is by Qabool et al. (2021), where ethical leaders, through self-efficacy, influence adherence to safety protocols.

To explore the mediating role of self-efficacy in the relationship between safety leadership and safety culture, it is essential to draw insights from relevant studies that have investigated similar mediating mechanisms in different contexts. For instance, Kim and Beehr (2017) demonstrated a favorable relationship between empowering leadership and self-efficacy, which in turn exhibited a negative association with deviant behaviors. While certain studies have highlighted a positive correlation between leadership and self-efficacy, others have suggested that this connection may not always be strong. Younas et al. (2018) found that creative self-efficacy does not significantly contribute to the relationship between ethical leadership and creativity. Similarly, Drukda (2022) observed no significant correlation between the occupational self-efficacy of teachers and the transformational leadership behaviour of principals in secondary schools.

Ke and Huang (2023) discovered that among Chinese college students, physical self-efficacy partly acted as a mediating factor in the relationship between transformational leadership and exercise adherence. According to Rehman and Zeb (2023) findings, self-efficacy functions as a mediator in the correlation between employees' green creativity and authentic leadership. This highlights the significance of self-belief in propelling desired behaviors within an organizational setting. Similarly, Chan (2024) found that group efficacy mediates the relationship between authoritarian leadership and followers' performance and that self-efficacy mediates the relationship between benevolent leadership and followers' performance. According to Khan et al. (2024), the self-efficacy of teachers acted as a mediator in the association between work satisfaction and instructional leadership, suggesting that self-efficacy plays a mediating role in the relationship between leadership and outcome. This result supports the theory that self-efficacy serves as a conduit by which leadership affects the attitudes and actions of subordinates.

All these studies highlight the significance of self-efficacy as a mediator in translating leadership behaviors into desired outcomes, which can be extrapolated to the domain of safety leadership and safety culture.

Therefore, based on these arguments, the following hypothesis is posited. Thus, it is hypothesized that:

H₂: Self-efficacy mediates the relationship between safety leadership and safety culture

SOCIAL SYSTEM THEORY

Social System Theory helps us understand the important effect of safety leadership on safety culture. According to its description, a social system is a network of interconnected roles inside a broader community made up of people and institutions that work together to create a functional society. Beliefs and knowledge, sentiment, purpose, ideas and norms, role, authority, and sanction are among the essential elements of a social structure (Social System Theory & Example, 2022).

A thorough grasp of the major impacts that safety leadership and safety culture have inside an organization can be obtained by applying Social System Theory to these topics. This idea states that safety leadership entails establishing and upholding safety norms and standards, encouraging good attitudes toward safety, and instilling and distributing beliefs and information about safety (Social System Theory & Example, 2022). It also entails integrating safety with the organization's objective. Leaders exert power to carry out safety policy implementation, clearly define roles and responsibilities related to safety, and set up consequences for safety infractions. By establishing a clear and visible goal for safety, these leadership acts encourage active group interactions and strengthen the bonds of interdependence that guarantee cooperation and shared accountability. These leadership initiatives result in a strong safety culture.

SOCIAL COGNITIVE THEORY

Social Cognitive Theory highlights the significance of cognitive, vicarious, self-regulatory, and self-reflective processes. Self-efficacy, or the conviction that one can control circumstances and bring about desired results, is a key idea in this theory. Their goal-setting techniques, way of thinking, and perseverance in the face of difficulty are all significantly impacted by this concept (Bandura, 2001).

Applying Social Cognitive Theory to the self-efficacy mediating effect shows that safety leadership raises employee self-efficacy, which in turn promotes a strong safety culture. When safety leaders set an example for others and support safe conduct, workers feel more empowered to make a positive impact on safety, which in turn motivates them to take proactive safety measures. Because of this increased self-efficacy, the organization's leadership and culture may better communicate, making safety an integral element of day-to-day operations and organizational culture.

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

The research framework establishes a connection between safety leadership, safety culture and self-efficacy, as depicted in Figure 1. By conducting an extensive examination of the available literature, this study has identified a deficiency, notably the lack of a comprehensive investigation within the context of the Malaysian construction industry. Consequently, this study presents a significant contribution to the existing body of knowledge and practices within the industry. This implies that self-efficacy may act as a mediator in the relationship between safety leadership and safety culture. Essentially, this study tackles the gap in research and highlights the significance of improving safety practices within the Malaysian construction industry.

Figure1. Research Framework.

METHODOLOGY

SAMPLE AND PROCEDURE

This study aimed to contribute original insights to the field and employed a quantitative approach within the positivist paradigm to ensure the generalizability of findings. Data were gathered through a cross-sectional survey using systematic random sampling from a population of 6,103 Grade G7 contractors from Selangor, Kuala Lumpur, Johor, and Pulau Pinang who were registered with the Malaysian Construction Industry Development Board (CIDB) as of 05 November 2022. (See Table 3).

Table 3. Numbers of G7 Contractors in Malaysia as of 05 November 2022

State	Numbers of G7 Contractors
Selangor	3,144
Kuala Lumpur	1,702
Johor	695
Pulau Pinang	562
Total	6,103

Source: Malaysian Construction Industry Development Board (CIDB), n.d.

The study adhered to sample selection criteria outlined by Saunders et al. (2016) whereby 370 contractors were chosen to serve as the sample size for this study. A 5-point Likert scale was used for data collection via Google Forms and self-administered survey questionnaires, distributed via email. Most online surveys had response rates of 33% on average, while paper-

based surveys had response rates of 56% (Nulty, 2018). However, a 30% response rate is acceptable (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Therefore, based on 33% response rate, 1,110 sets (370 x 3) of questionnaires—three times the sample size—were needed to be disseminated, to at least achieve 370 responses.

For the purpose of this study, a method known as systematic sampling was used, which referred to the strategy of sampling in which only the first unit was chosen at random, and the remaining units were selected automatically based on a pattern that had been predetermined (Mostafa & Ahmad, 2018).

The method entails choosing a sampling interval of five contractors. The sample is then expanded by adding each fifth contractor, starting at a random point, in this case is number 4, and continuing in this manner, until the target size of 1,110 (370 x 3) is achieved. The data collected from supervisors, engineers, and project managers working in construction firms (Grade G7 contractors) served as the unit of analysis.

A response rate of 34.68% out of 1,170 (385 replies) was considered acceptable. SmartPLS4, which is appropriate for estimating complex path models containing latent variables, and partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) were used to evaluate the data. The selection of PLS path modelling was based on its capacity to be applied to intricate real-world models, hence providing more precise predictions (Akhtar et al., 2017).

In the current research, safety leadership, safety culture, and self-efficacy questionnaires were administered to employees working for Grade G7 contractors in Malaysia. The primary objective of this study is to investigate the mediating effects of self-efficacy on the relationship between safety leadership and safety culture within Malaysia's construction industry.

MEASURES

The adoption of measurement instruments for safety culture, safety leadership, and self-efficacy from prior research is justified for the construction industry in Malaysia due to several reasons. Firstly, the concepts of safety culture, safety leadership, and self-efficacy are applicable to many industries and have been demonstrated to have a substantial effect on safety results, including construction. The chosen metrics have proven to have established validity and reliability in earlier research, confirming the findings' consistency and comparability. The items' contextual adjustments and the use of relevant terminology were among the necessary adaptations made to the instruments in order to customize them to the unique setting of the Malaysian construction industry.

A total of 32 items, divided into 12 questions about company safety culture, 10 questions about safety leadership, and 10 questions about self-efficacy, are used in the study questionnaires. The Safety Culture Scale (SCU) used in this research is based on the safety culture assessment questionnaire created by Díaz-Cabrera et al. (2007). There are twelve (12) items in the SCU survey questionnaire. This scale's reliability is validated by its 0.949 Cronbach's Alpha score. The Likert scale has five points: "Strongly Disagree = 1" to "Strongly Agree = 5". Respondents rank their views on this scale.

The ten-item Safety Leadership Scale (SLS), created by Wu et al. (2008), is used to measure safety leadership. The reliability of the scale is validated by Cronbach's Alpha of 0.921. Respondents rank their answers on a 5-point Likert scale, the same as in the SCU. Lastly, the Self-Efficacy Scale (SE), which consists of ten items created by Jerusalem and Schwarzer (1992), is used to evaluate self-efficacy. This scale's 0.924 Cronbach's Alpha rating indicates its

reliability. Respondents rank their answers using a 5-point Likert scale, just like on the other scales.

RESULTS

To ensure the integrity of the data for analysis, a thorough data screening and cleaning procedure was carried out before moving on to the measurement model analysis utilizing SmartPLS.

DATA SCREENING AND CLEANING

By computing z-scores for univariate outliers, the presence of outliers was evaluated. Since no significant outliers were found, no additional treatment was required. Skewness and kurtosis alone were used to assess normality because of the model's simplicity and SmartPLS's resilience to non-normal data. The findings showed that no changes were required because the data satisfied acceptable normality criteria. Lastly, the dataset's overall consistency. These procedures demonstrated that the data were trustworthy and reliable, making them suitable for the measurement model analysis without the need for any adjustments.

MEASUREMENT MODEL

Indicators and their relationships to pertinent latent variables were examined in the measurement model. Testing the measurement model's validity and reliability was essential to the assessment.

The measurement model for this study, which includes outer loadings and Cronbach's Alpha, is depicted in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Measurement Model.

As suggested by Hair et al. (2014), convergent validity was assessed using factor loadings, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE) (See Table 3).

Table 3. Test of Internal Consistency and Convergent Validity

Construct	Item	Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	Rho A	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Safety Culture (SCU)	SCU1	0.862	0.961	0.963	0.966	0.702
	SCU2	0.758				
	SCU3	0.905				
	SCU4	0.823				
	SCU5	0.870				
	SCU6	0.905				
	SCU7	0.890				
	SCU8	0.912				
	SCU9	0.791				
	SCU10	0.807				
	SCU11	0.749				
	SCU12	0.759				
Safety Leadership (SLS)	SLS1	0.801	0.950	0.952	0.957	0.691
	SLS2	0.833				
	SLS3	0.821				
	SLS4	0.738				
	SLS5	0.871				
	SLS6	0.821				
	SLS7	0.865				
	SLS8	0.861				
	SLS9	0.830				
	SLS10	0.864				
Self-Efficacy (SE)	SE1	0.749	0.945	0.946	0.953	0.669
	SE2	0.775				
	SE3	0.743				
	SE4	0.785				
	SE5	0.844				
	SE6	0.861				
	SE7	0.851				
	SE8	0.846				
	SE9	0.874				
	SE10	0.837				

Fornell-Larcker criterion and Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) were employed to assess discriminant validity, and the results are presented in Table 4 and Table 5.

Table 4. Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker)

Construct	SCU	SE	SLS
Safety Culture (SCU)	0.838		
Self-Efficacy (SE)	0.488	0.818	
Safety Leadership (SLS)	0.709	0.514	0.832

Table 5. Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

Construct	SCU	SE	SLS
Safety Culture (SCU)			
Self-Efficacy (SE)	0.507		
Safety Leadership (SLS)	0.733	0.533	

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is used to detect multicollinearity among predictor variables (See Table 6).

Table 6. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Construct	SCU	SE	SLS
Safety Culture (SCU)			
Self-Efficacy (SE)	1.359		
Safety Leadership (SLS)	1.359	1.000	

STRUCTURAL MODEL

Figure 3. Structural Model Direct Relationship and Mediating Effect

The subsequent stage in PLS analysis involved the construction of a structural model, which depicted the relationships among the hypothetical constructs. Table 7 provides information on R^2 , Q^2 and f^2 values.

Table 7. R^2 , Q^2 , and f^2 Values

Construct	R^2	Q^2 Predict	f^2 (SCU)	f^2 (SE)
Safety Culture (SCU)	0.505	0.479	-	-
Self-Efficacy (SE)	0.250	0.245	0.046	-
Safety Leadership (SLS)	-	-	0.560	0.334

Table 8 provided information on the significance testing for the direct relationships between variables. Hypotheses 1 (H_1) investigated the relationship between Safety Leadership and Safety Culture.

Table 8. Structural Model: Test of Significance for Direct Relationships and Mediating Relationships

Hypotheses	Relationship	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Path A Beta	Path B Beta	In-direct Effect (A*B)	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	Decision
H1	Safety Leadership -> Safety Culture	0.608	0.609	-	-	-	0.051	11.807	0.000	Supported
H2	Safety Leadership -> Self-Efficacy -> Safety Culture	-	-	0.500	0.173	0.0865	0.025	3.451	0.000	Supported

DISCUSSION

SmartPLS4 was used in this study's analysis. The PLS-SEM approach used in this study had two primary phases. The first phase, called the measurement model, was centred on assessing the validity and reliability of measurements. Following this, a structural model was created in the next stage of PLS analysis. In this stage, hypothesis testing and an exploration of the relationships between the variables found in the measurement model were carried out using PLS-SEM (Marcos et al., 2020).

INTERNAL CONSISTENCY

Strong internal consistency and reliability are shown by the study throughout all of its constructs. The Safety Culture (SCU), Safety Leadership (SLS), and Self-Efficacy (SE) Cronbach's Alpha coefficients are remarkably high at 0.961, 0.950, and 0.945, respectively. These values exceed the desirable threshold of 0.8 as well as the acceptable threshold of 0.7, demonstrating strong internal consistency within each construct. Moreover, the composite reliability (CR) values for SCU (0.966), SLS (0.957), and SE (0.953) demonstrate the constructs' high reliability by surpassing the 0.7 threshold and exceeding 0.9.

CONVERGENT VALIDITY

Strong factor loadings and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values demonstrate the study's strong convergent validity for its constructs. Safety Culture (SCU), Safety Leadership (SLS), and Self-Efficacy (SE) have factor loadings ranging from 0.749 to 0.912, 0.738 to 0.871, and 0.743 to 0.874, respectively. The majority of these loadings surpass the suggested criterion of 0.700, indicating significant item reliability. The AVE values for SCU (0.702), SLS (0.691), and SE (0.669) all exceed 0.5, indicating that more than 50% of the variance is explained by the constructs' indicators, thus confirming their strong convergent validity.

DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY

The results of the discriminant validity assessment using both Fornell & Larcker's criterion (Table 4) and the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT) (Table 5) support the distinctiveness of the constructs in the model. The square roots of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for Safety Culture (0.916), Self-Efficacy (0.905), and Safety Leadership (0.912) conform to Fornell & Larcker's criterion, indicating that each construct shares more variance with its own indicators than with indicators of other constructs (SCU-SE: 0.488, SCU-SLS: 0.709, SE-SLS: 0.514), indicating that each construct shares more variance with its own indicators than with indicators of other constructs. This implies that discriminant validity is sufficient. This finding that the constructs are sufficiently distinct is further supported by the fact that the HTMT ratios for each pair of constructs—Self-Efficacy with Safety Culture (0.507), Safety Leadership with Safety Culture (0.733), and Safety Leadership with Self-Efficacy (0.533)—are all below the suggested threshold of 0.85 (Kline, 2011).

VARIANCE INFLATION FACTOR

The predictors (SE and SLS) are not strongly correlated and may be utilized with confidence in the structural model since the VIF values are all significantly below 3, which indicates that there is no substantial multicollinearity among the constructs in the model.

MODEL FIT AND PREDICTIVE RELEVANCE ASSESSMENT

The coefficient of determination, or R^2 values, shows how much of the variance in the dependent variable can be predicted based on the independent variable (or variables). The R^2 value for Safety Culture (SCU) is 0.505. A moderate R^2 value of 0.50 indicates that the model somewhat explains the variance in safety culture; according to Hair et al. (2017), Self-Efficacy (SE), on the other hand, has an R^2 value of 0.250. An R^2 value of 0.25 is considered weak by Hair et al. (2017), indicating that the model only partially explains the variance in self-efficacy.

The model's predictive relevance is evaluated by the Q^2 values, which are obtained from the Stone-Geisser criterion. The Q^2 value for Safety Culture (SCU) is 0.479. A Q^2 value larger than 0 indicates that the exogenous constructs have predictive relevance for the endogenous constructs (Enis & Geisser, 1974; Hair et al., 2017; Stone, 1974). Since 0.479 is significantly greater than 0, the model has good predictive relevance for safety culture. Similarly, the Q^2 value for Self-Efficacy (SE) is 0.245. Being greater than 0, this Q^2 value signifies that the model also has predictive relevance for self-efficacy.

The f^2 values measure the effect size, indicating the impact of a specific predictor on the endogenous constructs. For Self-Efficacy (SE), the f^2 value for Safety Culture (SCU) is 0.046. According to Cohen (1988), an f^2 value of 0.046 is considered small, implying that safety culture has a small effect size on self-efficacy. Regarding Safety Leadership (SLS), the f^2 value for Safety Culture (SCU) is 0.560. An f^2 value of 0.560 is substantial, indicating a substantial effect size of safety leadership on safety culture. While the f^2 value for Safety Leadership (SLS) on Self-Efficacy (SE) is 0.334, which is considered medium (Cohen, 1988). This indicates that safety leadership has a medium effect size on self-efficacy.

TEST OF DIRECT AND MEDIATING RELATIONSHIPS

Hypothesis 1 (H_1) investigated the relationship between Safety Leadership and Safety Culture, and the results revealed a substantial relationship, with a sample T statistic of 11.807 and a corresponding p-value of 0.000, indicating strong statistical significance (See Table 8). Therefore, Hypothesis 1 was supported, suggesting a positive significant relationship between Safety Leadership and Safety Culture.

The findings clearly demonstrate a highly significant relationship between safety leadership and safety culture, thereby lending support to Hypotheses H_1 . This result backs the recent findings by Atikasari et al. (2022) and Indrayana et al. (2022). Effective safety leadership behaviors, such as promoting safe practices, fostering effective communication, leading by example, and supporting innovation, are intricately tied to the development and perpetuation of a positive safety culture. This synergy underscores the pivotal role of supervisors in shaping the safety culture and emphasizes the importance of aligning leadership practices with organizational values to cultivate a safer and more productive work environment. Organizations that recognize and nurture this connection are better poised to achieve their safety objectives while enhancing the well-being and engagement of their workforce.

Hypothesis 2 (H_2) examined the mediation effect of Self-Efficacy on Safety Leadership and Safety Culture. Table 7 provided bootstrapping results for indirect effects, offering insights into the mediation pathway. The analysis demonstrated that the beta coefficients for Path A (Safety Leadership \rightarrow Self-Efficacy) and Path B (Self-Efficacy \rightarrow Safety Culture) were 0.500 and 0.173, respectively. Consequently, the indirect effect ($A*B$) was calculated to be 0.086500. These findings suggest that Self-Efficacy indeed mediates the relationship between Safety Leadership and Safety Culture, with a moderate indirect effect observed.

Self-efficacy functioned as a crucial mediating factor, bridging the gap between safety leadership behaviors and the development of a robust safety culture within the organization.

This process can be succinctly summarized as follows: effective safety leadership practices enhanced employees' self-efficacy concerning safety-related tasks and responsibilities. This elevated self-efficacy subsequently led to heightened engagement, a positive attitude, and greater resilience in safety-related domains. These self-efficacy-driven behaviors and attitudes collectively contributed to the cultivation of a strong safety culture within the organization.

Many studies utilize self-efficacy as a mediator to understand the impact of different leadership styles on various variables. Surprisingly, none have thoroughly examined the mediating role of self-efficacy on the relationship between safety leadership and safety culture. The closest study with similar findings is by Qabool et al. (2021), where ethical leaders, through self-efficacy, influence adherence to safety protocols. Considering the lack of literature exploring the mediating influence of self-efficacy on the correlation between safety leadership and safety culture, this discovery represents the originality of the study, which aims to fill this gap.

In the construction industry, safety leadership plays a pivotal role in shaping a strong safety culture due to the high-risk nature of the work environment. Effective safety leadership involves demonstrating a commitment to safety, setting clear safety expectations, and actively engaging with employees to foster safe practices. These actions are essential in an industry where hazards are prevalent and the potential for accidents is high. Self-efficacy, or the belief in one's ability to execute safety-related tasks, mediates the relationship between safety leadership and safety culture. When construction leaders exhibit strong safety leadership behaviors, they enhance workers' confidence in their ability to perform tasks safely. This increased self-efficacy leads to greater adherence to safety protocols, proactive hazard identification, and a collective commitment to safety standards. As a result, a positive safety culture is cultivated, characterized by shared safety values, continuous safety improvements, and reduced incident rates. In the construction industry, where the consequences of unsafe practices can be severe, the development of self-efficacy among workers is particularly critical. It ensures that employees are not only aware of safety procedures but are also confident in their ability to implement them effectively. Therefore, the significant effect between safety leadership and safety culture, mediated by self-efficacy, is justified as it highlights the essential components required to maintain a safe and productive construction environment.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study demonstrated the significant positive effect of safety leadership on safety culture in the Malaysian construction industry, thereby lending support to Hypotheses 1 (H_1), which were supported by previous studies by Atikasari et al. (2022), and Indrayana et al. (2022). Positive safety cultures are closely linked to the establishment and ongoing cultivation of effective safety leadership behaviors, which include advocating for safe practices, cultivating effective communication, setting a good example, and encouraging innovation. This synergy highlights how supervisors play a critical role in establishing the safety culture and how important it is to align corporate values with leadership practices to foster a safer and more productive work environment. Establishments that acknowledge and foster this relationship will be in a better position to accomplish their safety goals while improving employee engagement and well-being. The findings of the study corroborated the Social System Theory, which maintained that organizational leaders' actions and behaviors had an impact on safety culture (H_1).

The results demonstrated convincingly that self-efficacy did, in fact, play a significant mediating role within the relationships between Safety Leadership and Safety Culture, providing substantial evidence that strongly supported the validity of Hypotheses 2 (H_2). In this

context, self-efficacy was the conviction that an individual can carry out activities competently, overcome obstacles, and accomplish desired results. Within the context of workplace safety, it represented an employee's confidence in their capacity to carry out safety-related duties, support safety initiatives, and adjust to changing safety regulations. In particular, self-efficacy was found to be an important mediator in the complex relationship between safety leadership and the establishment of a strong safety culture in an organization. Effective safety leadership, characterized by supervisors and managers prioritizing safety, setting a positive example, involving employees in safety decisions, and supporting safety initiatives, impacted employees' perceptions of their own safety-related abilities. The mediation process between safety leadership and safety culture, involving self-efficacy, unfolded in the following manner. Effective safety leadership practices raised employees' self-efficacy by influencing their views of their safety-related abilities. As a result, the organization's safety culture was shaped by encouraging greater employee engagement, a positive outlook on safety, and the development of resilience in the face of safety challenges. This finding reflects the uniqueness of the study, which attempts to close the gap in the literature by examining the mediating role of self-efficacy on the relationship between safety leadership and safety culture. The empirical results of the study validated the fundamental concepts of Social Cognitive Theory, highlighting the significance of self-efficacy—that is, workers' confidence in their ability to engage in safe behaviors. This idea was fundamental to the way safety leadership promoted a healthy safety culture inside the organization. In other words, when employees had confidence in their ability to perform safe actions, it enhanced the effectiveness of safety leadership in promoting a strong safety culture within the organization (H₂).

Several recommendations can be made for future research. Initially, cross-cultural comparisons can provide a significant understanding of how safety culture appears in various cultural contexts. Researchers can find cultural elements that affect safety practices by examining the variations and commonalities in safety attitudes, actions, and perceptions among cultural groups. With this comparative approach, it is possible to build culturally aware safety performance enhancement techniques.

Second, using longitudinal study designs can shed light on how safety culture has changed over time within organizations. By monitoring alterations in safety culture over a period of time, researchers can detect patterns, paths, and possible factors that influence cultural transformations. Organizational safety initiatives are backed by longitudinal studies, which also allow the examination of causal relationships and the assessment of the long-term efficacy of safety actions.

Furthermore, the integration of qualitative research approaches with quantitative research can provide a more profound comprehension of the fundamental mechanisms and contextual elements that influence safety culture. Through qualitative methods like focus groups, interviews, and observation, researchers can examine people's individualized experiences, opinions, and perceptions of safety culture. This qualitative investigation offers subtle insights that quantitative approaches would miss, enhancing theory-building and directing real-world interventions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The assistance for publishing this research was provided by UNITAR International University, for which the authors are grateful.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

In this study, there is no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- Akhtar, W., Ghufuran, H., Husnain, M., & Shahid, A. (2017). The Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Employee's Job Performance: The Moderating Role of Perceived Organizational Support. *Journal of Accounting & Marketing*, 6(3), 2-8. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2168-9601.1000243>
- Arina Sofiah (2023, December 14). *Updates on DOSM's AES 2022 Employment and Salaries & Wages Statistics*. Human Resources Online.net. <https://www.humanresourcesonline.net/updates-on-dosm-s-aes-2022-employment-and-salaries-wages-statistics>
- Atikasari, C. D., Sudiarno, A., & Priyanto, E. (2022). The Effect of Safety Leadership, Safety Culture, and Safety Behavior on Safety Performance After a Company Merger: A Case Study. *Jurnal Sistem dan Manajemen Industri*, 6(2), 187-199. <https://doi.org/10.30656/jsmi.v6i2.5051>
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The Exercise of Control*. Freeman.
- Bandura, A. (2001). Social Cognitive Theory: An Agentic Perspective. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52(1), 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.52.1.1>
- Boadu, E. F., Wang, C. C., & Sunindijo, R. Y. (2020). Characteristics of the Construction Industry in Developing Countries and Its Implications for Health and Safety: An Exploratory Study in Ghana. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(11), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17114110>
- Chan, S. C. (2024). Paternalistic leadership, efficacy beliefs and followers' performance: testing a multilevel model. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 45(3), 442-460. <https://doi.org/10.1108/lodj-04-2022-0175>
- Choudhry, R. M., Fang, D., & Mohamed, S. (2007). The Nature of Safety Culture: A Survey of The State-of-The-Art. *Safety Science*, 45(10), 993-1012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2006.09.003>
- CIDB. (n.d.). CIDB. cims.cidb.gov.my. <https://cims.cidb.gov.my/SMIS/regcontractor/reglocalsearchcontractor.vbhtml>

- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences*. (2nd ed.). Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Publishers
- Díaz-Cabrera, D., Hernández-Fernaud, E., & Isla-Díaz, R. (2007). An Evaluation of a New Instrument to Measure Organisational Safety Culture Values and Practices. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 39(6), 1202-1211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2007.03.005>
- Drukda, N. (2022). Effectiveness of Teachers in Relation to Leadership of Principals in Bhutan: A Case of Secondary Schools from Trashigang District. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, 10(10), 5-22. <https://doi.org/10.22214/ijraset.2022.46939>
- Eden, D. & Zuk, Y. (1995). Seasickness as a Self-Fulfilling Prophecy: Raising Self-Efficacy to Boost Performance at Sea. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 80, 628-635. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.80.5.628>
- Enis, P., & Geisser, S. (1974). Optimal predictive linear discriminants. *The Annals of Statistics*, 403-410.
- Fang, D., & Wu, H. (2013). Development of a Safety Culture Interaction (SCI) Model for Construction Projects. *Safety Science*, 57, 138-149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2013.02.003>
- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Structural Equation Models with Unobservable Variables and Measurement Error: Algebra and Statistics. *Sage Journals*, 18(3).
- Gardner, D.G. & Pierce, J.L. (1998). Self-Esteem and Self-Efficacy Within the Organizational Context. *Group & Organization Management*, 23(1), 48-70. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1059601198231004>
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., & Thiele, K. O. (2017). Mirror, Mirror on the Wall: A Comparative Evaluation of Composite-Based Structural Equation Modeling Methods. *Journal of The Academy of Marketing Science*, 45(5), 616-632.
- Hair Jr, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L., & Kuppelwieser, V. G. (2014). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM): An Emerging Tool in Business Research. *European Business Review*, 26(2), 106-121. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-10-2013-0128>
- Indrayana, D. V., Pribadi, K. S., Marzuki, P. F., & Iridiastadi, H. (2022, July). *Factors Affecting Safety Leadership of Construction Project Owners in Indonesia*. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1065, No. 1, p. 012003). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1065/1/012003>
- Ishak, N., & Azizan, M. A. (2018, February). *A Review on the Benchmarking Concept in Malaysian Construction Safety Performance*. AIP Conference Proceedings, 1930(1), 020024-1-020024-5. AIP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5022918>
- Jerusalem, M., & Schwarzer, R. (1992). Self-efficacy as a Resource Factor in Stress Appraisal Processes. *Self-Efficacy: Thought Control of Action* (pp. 195-213). Routledge.
- Ke, W., & Huang, J. (2023). Relationship between Chinese College Students' Perceived Transformational Leadership by Physical Education Teachers and Their Exercise Adherence: The Mediating Role of Physical Self-Efficacy. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 18(7), 173-180. <https://doi.org/10.5897/ERR2023.4336>
- Khan, F., Preeti & Gupta, V. (2024). Examining the relationships between instructional leadership, teacher self-efficacy and job satisfaction: a study of primary schools in India.

Journal of Educational Administration, 62(2), 223-238. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEA-09-2022-0145>

Khasanah, N., Kholil, K., & Sugiarto, S. (2019). Analysis the Effect of Leadership to Safety Climate, Safety Culture and Safety Performance. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*, 4(2), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajarr/2019/v4i230106>

Kim, M., & Beehr, T. A. (2017). Self-efficacy and Psychological Ownership Mediate the Effects of Empowering Leadership on Both Good and Bad Employee Behaviours. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 24(4), 466-478. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1548051817702078>

Kline, R. B. (2011). *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling*. New York Guilford.

Lee, S. E., & Quinn, B. L. (2020). Safety Culture and Patient Safety Outcomes in East Asia: A Literature Review. *Western Journal of Nursing Research*, 42(3), 220-230. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0193945919848755>

Ma, Y., Wu, C., Fang, D., & Wang, C. (2018). Safety Leadership Effectiveness Assessment of Project Managers in the Construction Industry: A Case Study of China. *Proceeding of Construction Research Congress 2018*, 314-323. <https://doi.org/10.1061/9780784481288.031>

Machfudiyanto, R. A., & Latief, Y. (2019, April). *Critical Success Factors to Improve Safety Culture on Construction Project in Indonesia*. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science 258(1) 1-11. IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/258/1/012016>

Marcos, A., García-Ael, C., & Topa, G. (2020). The Influence of Work Resources, Demands, and Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, and Citizenship Behaviors of Spanish Police Officers. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(20), 7607. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17207607>

Mohammad, M. Z., & Hadikusumo, B. H. (2019). Overview of Safety Behaviour and Safety Culture in The Malaysian Construction Industry. *Construction Health and Safety in Developing Countries* (pp. 218-233). Routledge.

Mohammadi, A., Tavakolan, M., & Khosravi, Y. (2018). Factors Influencing Safety Performance on Construction Projects: A Review. *Safety Science*, 109(December 2017), 382-397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2018.06.017>

Mostafa, S. A., & Ahmad, I. A. (2018). Recent Developments in Systematic Sampling: A Review. *Journal of Statistical Theory and Practice*, 12(2), 290-310. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15598608.2017.1353456>

Novaryan, O. Y., & Erwandi, D. E. (2024). Corelationship Between Contractor Safety Management and Safety Leadership: Systematic Review. *Jurnal Kesehatan Mesencephalon*, 10(1). <http://dx.doi.org/10.36053/mesencephalon.v10i1.426>

Nulty, D. D. (2008). The Adequacy of Response Rates to Online and Paper Surveys: What Can Be Done? *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 33(3), 301-314. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602930701293231>

Oah, S., Na, R., & Moon, K. (2018). The Influence of Safety Climate, Safety Leadership, Workload, and Accident Experiences on Risk Perception: A Study of Korean

Manufacturing Workers. *Safety and Health at Work*, 9(4), 427-433.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2018.01.008>

Odu, J. O., Rahmawati, H. T., & Juliana, J. (2018). Safety Culture Among the Staff at a Public University in Malaysia. *International Journal of Public Health and Clinical Sciences*, 5(4), 161-174.

Official Website Department of Occupational Safety and Health - Occupational Accident Statistics. (n.d.). <https://www.dosh.gov.my/index.php/statistic-v/occupational-accident-statistics>

Pillay, K., & Haupt, T. (2008, March). The Cost of Construction Accidents: An Exploratory Study. In *14th International Conference on Evolution and Directions in Construction Safety and Health* (pp. 456-464).

Perry, P. (2016). Health and safety culture. *Health and Safety Questions and Answers: A Practical Approach* (pp. 121-130). ICE Publishing.

Qabool, S., Jalees, T., Aziz, A., Anwar, A., & Pahi, M. H. (2021). Consequences of Ethical Leadership with the Mediating Role of Self-Efficacy and Workplace Climate. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 20(4), 1-13.

Rehman, F. U., & Zeb, A. (2023). Investigating the nexus between authentic leadership, employees' green creativity, and psychological environment: evidence from emerging economy. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(49), 107746-107758.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-29928-1>

Saleh, A. M., Darawad, M. W., & Al-Hussami, M. (2015). The Perception of Hospital Safety Culture and Selected Outcomes Among Nurses: An Exploratory Study. *Nursing & Health Sciences*, 17(3), 339-346. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nhs.12196>

Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2016). *Research Methods for Business Students* (7th ed.). Pearson Education Limited.

Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research Methods for Business* (7th ed.). John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-0753-5_102084

Social System Theory & Example (2022, August 31). In *Study.com*.
<https://study.com/learn/lesson/social-system-theory-examples.html>

Stone, M. (1974). Cross-validation and multinomial prediction. *Biometrika*, 61(3), 509-515.

Van Nunen, K., Li, J., Reniers, G., & Ponnet, K. (2018). Bibliometric analysis of safety culture research. *Safety Science*, 108, 248-258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2017.08.011>

Wu, C., Li, N., & Fang, D. (2017). Leadership improvement and its impact on workplace safety in construction projects: A conceptual model and action research. *International Journal of Project Management*, 35(8), 1495-1511. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2017.08.013>

Wu, C., Wang, F., Zou, P. X. W., & Fang, D. (2016). How safety leadership works among owners, contractors and subcontractors in construction projects. *International Journal of Project Management*, 34(5), 789-805. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2016.02.013>

Wu, T. C., Chen, C. H., & Li, C. C. (2008). A Correlation Among Safety Leadership, Safety Climate and Safety Performance. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 21(3), 307-318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlpp.2007.11.001>

Wu, T. C., Lin, C. H., & Shiau, S. Y. (2010). Predicting Safety Culture: The Roles of Employer, Operations Manager and Safety Professional. *Journal of Safety Research*, 41 (5), 423-431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsr.2010.06.006>

Younas, A., Wang, D., Javed, B., Rawwas, M. Y. A., Abdullah, I., & Zaffar, M. A. (2018). Positive Psychological States and Employee Creativity: The Role of Ethical Leadership. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, 54 (3), 567-581. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.391>